

A VECTOR NEAR-FIELD SCANNER FOR INTER-BAND ILLUMINATION AND BEAM CO-ALIGNMENT

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The Submillimeter Array (SMA) operates in three bands: 200 (180–250 GHz) or 300 (266–355 GHz) and 400 (320–420 GHz). Overlapping coverage in the orthogonally polarized 300 and 400 bands allows full Stokes operation. Co-alignment of the beams in all bands, 300/400 in particular, is important. A vector near-field scanner is used to measure and correct misalignments arising from receiver replacements in the field.

The scanner measures the aperture E-field by scanning a WR-3 open wave-guide transmitter probe in a plane in the beam-wave-guide system where images of the subreflector and the receiver feed-horns are formed. The 10-dB point in this plane is ~ 25 mm. A square raster, up to 50 mm, can be scanned on-the-fly, typical maps being 35-mm, made in ~ 6 minutes. The signal is received by the standard science receivers.

SPECIAL LO BOARD

BLOCK DIAGRAM

SCANNED TRANSMITTER

BEAM WAVE-GUIDE

The system uses existing YIG references in the cabin: YIG1(2) for locking the receiver LO; YIG2(1) is multiplied up (x 36) to generate the transmitted tone in the 200/300 band.

To achieve coherence needed for phase measurements, a 1.7 GHz reference tone is generated in the special LO system by mixing the Gunn output and YIG2. This reference is used in the scanner down converter to produce a 100 MHz tone to lock a vector-voltmeter. The transmitter signal from the receiver at 5.1 GHz is down converted to 100 MHz using the same reference to feed the signal channel of the vector-voltmeter.

optics insert mirrors
optical elements adjusted : combiner / grid

SMA Near Field Scanner, Amplitude

The resulting amplitude map is directly used to assess the centration of the illumination. The measurements also verify the 10-dB size of ~ 25 mm.

A spherical wave front and a gradient are fitted to the phase map. The gradients measure the pointing offsets.

Co-alignment is achieved by adjusting the optical elements identified above and verified by a new map.

The turn around time for an adjustment and mapping is ~ 30 minutes.

Pointing co-alignment to better than 5" has been achieved on one antenna (No. 8) and measurements on more antennas are under way.

SMA Near Field Scanner, Phase

Contours: 10,20,30,40 deg.